

Assessment of Diurnal Variations in Nutritional Components of Raw Milk of a Grazing White Fulani Cow in Obinze, Owerri West Local Government Area, Imo State.

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Abstract: This study aimed to assess the diurnal variations in the nutritional composition of raw cow milk from grazing White Fulani cows in Obinze, Owerri West Local Government Area, Imo State. Specific objectives include; examining milk composition, comparing morning and evening variations, investigating daily fluctuations and formulating recommendations. The study involved four mid-lactation White Fulani cows, and milk was sampled both morning and evening over ten days. Results revealed significant ($P < 0.05$) variations in moisture content and total solids between morning ($84.78 \pm 0.02\%$ and $11.66 \pm 0.02\%$) and evening ($87.52 \pm 0.01\%$ and $9.70 \pm 0.02\%$) respectively in milk samples, with no daily variations. Sodium (1943.39 ± 1.56 mg/l and 1961.11 ± 3.75 mg/l), calcium (778.92 ± 0.20 mg/l and 781.14 ± 0.47 mg/l) and magnesium (1895.34 ± 1.23 mg/l to 1909.39 ± 2.98 mg/l) concentrations varied ($P < 0.05$) between morning and evening samples, with daily fluctuations ($P < 0.05$). This highlights that cow milk is rich in proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals. However, time of milking affects the complexity of milk composition and its constant variation and is therefore to be considered a priority in cow milk production. There is also need for further research to enhance understanding and provide future reference materials.

Keywords: *Diurnal variations, nutritional components, raw milk, milk composition*

Introduction

Milk, a nutrient-rich liquid produced by the mammary glands of mammals, serves as the primary nutrition source for infant mammals before they can consume other foods (Damtew and Aregay, 2020). It is a white fluid containing fat globules, casein albumin, sugar, and inorganic salt, designed by nature

to be a complete food for young mammals (Selvagi, 2014). According to Ramesh (2016), its major components include water (87.40%), milk solids (12.60%), fat (3.60%), protein (3.40%), lactose (4.90%), and minerals (0.70%).

Van Hlzen *et al.* (2019) posited that milk is rich in minerals like calcium, phosphorous,

sodium, potassium, chlorine, iodine, magnesium, and a small amount of iron, vital for bone growth. These minerals constitute a significant portion in milk but varies based on factors such as lactation stage, nutritional status, genetics, season, and animal health. The nutritional importance of milk extends to macro and micronutrients, making it a key contributor to meeting dietary needs and plays a crucial role in household food security (Foley *et al.*, 2012).

Cow milk dominates global milk production (782 million tons in 2013), comprising 85 % of the world's supply, followed by buffalo (11 %), doe (2.3 %), ewe (1.4 %), and camel (0.2 %) (Damtew and Aregay, 2020). Foley *et al.* (2012) posited that cow milk is the most universal raw material for dairy product processing, and undergoes changes in composition during lactation, and is influenced by various factors, including genetics.

In Nigeria, despite cow milk being the primary raw material, its production relies heavily on traditional pastoral systems. There's a need for a gradual transformation to meet evolving consumer demands (Mowang *et al.*, 2017). The variability in milk composition within breeds is attributed to complex genetic polymorphism (Malacarne *et al.*, 2014).

Numerous research studies have explored the fluctuations in cow milk components,

considering factors such as season, lactation states, cow age, health, and nutrition (Hakoueu *et al.*, 2021; Van Hlzen *et al.*, 2019; Malacarne *et al.*, 2014; Walshe *et al.*, 2011). Surprisingly, limited information exists regarding diurnal variations, prompting the need for this particular study. Therefore, this study assessed the diurnal variation of nutritional components of raw milk of a grazing White Fulani Cow in Obinze, Owerri West Local Government Area, Imo State.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was carried out in Obinze in Owerri West L.G.A. of Imo State, with geographical coordinates of 5° 25' 0'' North and 6° 58' 0'' East. Obinze is a village in southern Nigeria situated along km12 port Harcourt road, and comprising six clans: Umuagam, Obokwu, Umuekpu, Umueje, Umueroroche and Umuanunu. The climate of Obinze community is typically tropical, which lies between the tropics of cancer and Capricorn. There are two major seasons, the dry and the rainy season which correspond with the predominance wind flow from the two laden south westerlies (tropical maritime air masses) and dry north easterlies (tropical continental air masses) that brings about the climate of Nigeria. The annual rainfall in the study area is the same with that of Imo state and is between 2000

mm and 2200 mm annually, July and September being the peak periods of the rainy season with a short spell in August as break (NIMET, 2017). The temperature of the study area is relatively high and varies from one season to another. The average annual temperature is 22°C. Annual minimum and maximum temperature are 28°C and 33°C from January to March. The mean maximum temperature usually occurs in January (NIMET, 2017).

Sample collection

Milk samples were collected from four (4) randomly selected and labelled white Fulani cows twice a day; in the morning between 06.00 hrs and 07.30 hrs before grazing and evening between 17.00 hrs and 18.30 hrs for ten (10) days making eighty (80) samples in all, through conventional hand milking method. The milk samples were collected with separate containers. To avoid contamination, containers set for sample collection were sterilized by soaking in 10% nitric acid (HNO₃) for 24 hours, then in distilled water and finally dried ready. The milk samples collected were taken to FECOLART laboratory for analysis.

Sample preparation

The collected milk samples were prepared using microwave-assisted acid digestion (Lee *et al.*, 2022). 3.0 cm³ of each liquid milk sample was transferred into a 60 cm³

Teflon digestion vessel and then optimized volumes of 6cm³ of 70 % nitric acid and 1ml of 30 % hydrogen peroxide were added and the mixture was shaken carefully and kept for 10minutes before closing the vessel. The samples were subjected to microwave digestion. After heating, the samples were cooled to room temperature to avoid foaming. The digested samples were diluted to 25 ml with deionized water and used for analysis. Blanks and reference material were run with the samples.

Proximate composition

Proximate analysis was carried out according to standard method described by AOAC, (2012) to determine the ash content, crude protein, crude fibre, fat content, dry matter as well as carbohydrate (nitrogen free extract) composition of the blends.

Elemental composition

Sodium, calcium and magnesium concentrations of the samples were determined using EDTA titration.

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as mean ± standard error mean (SEM) and statistically analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Means were separated at 5 % level of significance using Fisher's least significant difference.

Results and Discussion

Variations in proximate compositions (ash, total solid and solid-non fat) of fresh cow milk

Table 1 Daily variations in ash, total solid and solid-non fat contents of cow milk

Sampling Days	Ash (%)			Total Solid (%)			Solid-Non Fat (%)		
	Morni ng	Eveni ng	P > 0.05	Morni ng	Eveni ng	P < 0.05	Morni ng	Eveni ng	P > 0.05
Day 1	0.46 ±0.07	0.53 ±0.04	NS	11.56 ±0.02	9.63 ±0.01	1.78	6.97 ±0.02	5.93 ±0.01	NS
Day 2	0.45 ±0.03	0.56 ±0.03	NS	11.57 ±0.02	9.66 ±0.01	1.80	7.01 ±0.01	5.93 ±0.02	NS
Day 3	0.48 ±0.06	0.54 ±0.15	NS	11.67 ±0.08	9.62 ±0.04	1.79	6.98 ±0.07	5.94 ±0.04	NS
Day 4	0.46 ±0.03	0.57 ±0.08	NS	11.61 ±0.04	9.71 ±0.02	1.80	7.03 ±0.02	5.98 ±0.02	NS
Day 5	0.48 ±0.03	0.56 ±0.09	NS	11.71 ±0.05	9.68 ±0.02	1.81	7.04 ±0.02	5.98 ±0.02	NS
Day 6	0.46 ±0.03	0.58 ±0.09	NS	11.64 ±0.05	9.73 ±0.02	1.82	7.05 ±0.02	5.99 ±0.02	NS
Day 7	0.48 ±0.03	0.57 ±0.08	NS	11.75 ±0.04	9.69 ±0.02	1.82	7.06 ±0.02	6.00 ±0.02	NS
Day 8	0.46 ±0.05	0.58 ±0.14	NS	11.59 ±0.08	9.73 ±0.03	1.81	7.03 ±0.05	5.98 ±0.03	NS
Day 9	0.48 ±0.06	0.56 ±0.15	NS	11.76 ±0.08	9.77 ±0.04	1.82	7.04 ±0.05	5.99 ±0.04	NS
Day 10	0.47 ±0.04	0.60 ±0.10	NS	11.75 ±0.05	9.77 ±0.02	1.84	7.09 ±0.01	6.03 ±0.02	NS
P > 0.05	NS	NS		NS	NS		NS	NS	

Results are expressed as (Mean ± SEM) of measurements; NS = Not significant at 5% probability level

The ash content of morning milk ranges between $0.45 \pm 0.03\%$ and $0.048 \pm 0.06\%$, the lowest being day two and the highest being day three and day nine respectively. The mean ash content for ten days stands at $0.47 \pm 0.01\%$ and 45.14% with no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The evening milk had ash content that ranged between $0.53 \pm 0.04\%$ and $0.60 \pm 0.10\%$ respectively with the ten days mean value of $0.57 \pm 0.01\%$. There was non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Though the ash value in the evening milk sample was higher (54.86%) than that of the morning (45.14%), there was no significant difference at $P > 0.05$. This value was similar to the report of Nina *et al* 2011 (0.4%), but lower than the value (0.70%) reported by Ramesh (2016). The variations may be attributed to feeding and the season/weather as postulated by Van Hlzen *et al.* (2019) and Nickerson (2009).

For Total Solid, the variations in the morning milk samples ranged from $11.56 \pm 0.02\%$ and $11.76 \pm 0.08\%$ with day one being the lowest and day nine recording the highest value respectively. The average mean value was $11.66 \pm 0.02\%$ with no significant difference observed. The evening value for total solid ranged between $9.62 \pm 0.04\%$ and $9.77 \pm 0.04\%$ respectively, day three being the lowest and day nine being the highest with the ten days mean value of $9.70 \pm 0.02\%$. There was non-significant effect in the evening milk total solid.

However, the mean value of morning total solid (54.59%) was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than the evening value (45.41%). This value was also less than the value (12.60%) reported by Ramesh (2016). This variation may also be attributed to feeding, season, environment, breed etc. (Van Hlzen *et al.*, 2019, Nickerson, 2009).

For Solid-Not-Fat (SNF), the daily mean value for morning samples ranged from $6.97 \pm 0.02\%$ to $7.09 \pm 0.01\%$ with the lowest being day one and the highest being day ten respectively, average mean value was $7.03 \pm 0.01\%$ with non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Meanwhile, the daily mean variation of the evening SNF in the milk ranged between $5.93 \pm 0.01\%$ and $6.03 \pm 0.02\%$ respectively with average mean value of $5.98 \pm 0.01\%$. There was non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$) variation between morning (54.06%) and evening (45.94%) SNF content of the milk. The value was similar to the value reported by Nina *et al* (2011).

Variations in fat, protein and carbohydrate contents of fresh cow milk

Table 2 Daily variations in fat, protein and carbohydrate contents of cow milk

Sampling Days	Fat (%)			Protein (%)			Carbohydrate (%)		
	Morning	Evening	P > 0.05	Morning	Evening	P > 0.05	Morning	Evening	P > 0.05
Day 1	4.56 ±0.05	3.70 ±0.02	NS	3.81 ±0.04	4.48 ±0.01	NS	16.41 ±0.02	15.07 ±0.01	NS
Day 2	4.59 ±0.10	3.72 ±0.04	NS	3.78 ±0.04	4.52 ±0.03	NS	16.32 ±0.02	15.03 ±0.01	NS
Day 3	4.59 ±0.20	3.71 ±0.09	NS	3.79 ±0.20	4.40 ±0.08	NS	16.31 ±0.08	15.03 ±0.03	NS
Day 4	4.63 ±0.20	3.72 ±0.02	NS	3.75 ±0.20	4.50 ±0.01	NS	16.15 ±0.08	14.97 ±0.03	NS
Day 5	4.59 ±0.30	3.70 ±0.02	NS	3.78 ±0.20	4.47 ±0.02	NS	16.29 ±0.10	15.02 ±0.04	NS
Day 6	4.66 ±0.30	3.72 ±0.03	NS	3.73 ±0.20	4.52 ±0.03	NS	16.04 ±0.11	14.92 ±0.04	NS
Day 7	4.61 ±0.30	3.70 ±0.03	NS	3.77 ±0.20	4.46 ±0.03	NS	16.21 ±0.10	14.99 ±0.04	NS
Day 8	4.67 ±0.30	3.73 ±0.05	NS	3.73 ±0.20	4.52 ±0.04	NS	15.99 ±0.13	14.90 ±0.05	NS
Day 9	4.62 ±0.40	3.71 ±0.05	NS	3.77 ±0.30	4.44 ±0.04	NS	16.21 ±0.14	14.99 ±0.06	NS
Day 10	4.75 ±0.40	3.73 ±0.07	NS	3.67 ±0.0.30	4.54 ±0.06	NS	15.69 ±0.16	14.79 ±0.06	NS
P > 0.05	NS	NS		NS	NS		NS	NS	

Results are expressed as (mean ± SEM) of measurements; NS = Not significant at 5% probability level

The daily morning mean value of fat ranged between 4.56 ± 0.05 % and 4.75 ± 0.40 %, the lowest mean value being day one and the highest mean value being day ten respectively with the average mean value of 4.63 ± 0.02 % and non-significant different at $P > 0.05$. The evening daily mean value ranged between 3.70 ± 0.02 % and 3.73 ± 0.07 %, the lowest mean value being day one and the highest being day ten respectively with the average mean value of 3.71 ± 0.01 %. The morning fat mean value was higher than the value (3.60%) reported by Ramesh (2016) but the evening mean value was at the range (3.90%) reported by Guetouache *et al* (2014). These fluctuations may be due to feeding, season, environment, breed etc. (Van Hlzen *et al* 2019, Nickerson, 2009).

Daily mean of protein ranged from 3.67 ± 0.03 % to 3.81 ± 0.04 %, the lowest being the value of day ten and the highest being the value of day one respectively with the average mean value of 3.76 ± 0.01 % with non-significant variation at $P > 0.05$. The evening daily mean value of protein ranged between 4.44 ± 0.04 % and 4.54 ± 0.06 % respectively with day nine value being the lowest and day ten recording the highest with the average of 4.49 ± 0.01 %. There was a non-significant variation ($P > 0.05$) between the morning mean value (45.59 %) and evening mean value (54.41 %) of protein. Values obtained in this work was

higher than the values reported by other researchers. Ahmed *et al.* (2014) and Medhammar *et al.* (2012) reported 3.19 ± 0.09 while Guetouache *et al.* (2014) reported the value of 3.5 %. The differences may be due to feeding management regime, including the type and quality of feed, feeding frequency, supplementation, and the cows' health and lactation stage, which according to Guetouache *et al.* (2014), directly influence milk composition.

The morning daily mean value of carbohydrate was found to range between 15.69 ± 0.16 % and 16.41 ± 0.02 % with day ten being lowest while day one was the highest respectively. The average mean value was 16.16 ± 0.07 %. There was non-significant difference in the daily mean value at $P > 0.05$, suggesting that the changes observed were not enough to be considered meaningful. This may be attributed to the relative stability of carbohydrate content in milk due to the consistent production of lactose, feeding management and physiological processes during lactation. Whereas, the evening mean value of carbohydrate ranged between 14.79 ± 0.06 % and 15.07 ± 0.01 % with day ten being the lowest and day one being the highest respectively having the average mean value of 14.97 ± 0.03 %. There was non-significant difference in the daily mean value at $P > 0.05$.

Variations in lactose and casein contents of fresh cow milk

Table 3 Daily variations in lactose and casein contents of cow milk

Sampling Days	Lactose (%)			Casein (%)		
	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05	Morning	Evening	P > 0.05
Day 1	4.44 ±0.02	4.06 ±0.01	NS	3.07 ±0.03	3.60 ±0.01	NS
Day 2	4.46 ±0.03	4.09 ±0.02	NS	3.06 ±0.03	3.62 ±0.03	NS
Day 3	4.46 ±0.01	4.03 ±0.04	NS	3.03 ±0.10	3.65 ±0.06	NS
Day 4	4.48 ±0.01	4.08 ±0.01	NS	3.03 ±0.10	3.60 ±0.01	NS
Day 5	4.46 ±0.01	4.06 ±0.01	NS	3.02 ±0.10	3.61 ±0.02	NS
Day 6	4.49 ±0.01	4.08 ±0.01	NS	2.98 ±0.20	3.57 ±0.02	NS
Day 7	4.47 ±0.01	4.06 ±0.01	NS	2.98 ±0.20	3.57 ±0.02	NS
Day 8	4.50 ±0.02	4.09 ±0.02	NS	2.98 ±0.20	3.56 ±0.03	NS
Day 9	4.47 ±0.02	4.05 ±0.02	NS	2.97 ±0.20	3.56 ±0.03	NS
Day 10	4.53 ±0.02	4.10 ±0.03	NS	2.94 ±0.20	3.53 ±0.05	NS
P > 0.05	NS	NS		NS	NS	

Results are expressed as (Mean ± SEM) of measurements; NS = Not significant at 5% probability level

The morning mean value of lactose ranged between 4.44 ±0.02 % and 4.53 ±0.02 % with day ten having the highest mean value and day one having the least mean value respectively with the average mean value of 4.48 ±0.01 % with no significant difference in morning lactose at P > 0.05. The evening daily mean value ranged from 4.03 ±0.04 % to 4.10 ±0.03 % with day three being the lowest and day ten the highest respectively with average mean value of 4.07 ±0.01 %. Though there were variations in the morning (52.38 %) and evening (47.62 %) mean value, there was non-significant difference at P > 0.05 among the daily samples. These mean values were closed to the values (4.03

± 0.03) reported by Ahmed *et al.* (2014) and Medhammar *et al.* (2012).

For casein, the morning mean value ranged between 2.94 ±0.02 % and 3.07 ±0.03 % with the the highest recorded in day one and the lowest in day ten respectively, with average mean value of 3.01 ±0.01 %. While the evening mean values ranged between 3.53 ±0.05 % and 3.65 ±0.06 %. The highest mean value was found to be on day three whereas the lowest was day ten respectively with average mean value of 3.59 ±0.01 %. Variations were observed between the morning (45.59 %) and evening (54.41 %) casein, but did not show difference at P > 0.05 across the daily samples.

Variations in yield and moisture content of fresh cow milk

Table 4 Daily variations in moisture contents and yield of cow milk

Sampling Days	Daily milk Yield (kg)			Moisture Content (%)		
	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05
Day 1	4.79 ±0.01	3.22 ±0.02	NS	84.89 ±0.02	87.56 ±0.01	2.11
Day 2	4.82 ±0.01	3.16 ±0.01	NS	84.82 ±0.01	87.54 ±0.01	2.12
Day 3	4.75 ±0.04	3.23 ±0.06	NS	84.90 ±0.07	87.58 ±0.03	2.13
Day 4	4.79 ±0.02	3.10 ±0.03	NS	84.74 ±0.04	87.50 ±0.02	2.13
Day 5	4.74 ±0.02	3.15 ±0.03	NS	84.80 ±0.04	87.54 ±0.02	2.14
Day 6	4.77 ±0.02	3.07 ±0.03	NS	84.70 ±0.04	87.49 ±0.02	2.14
Day 7	4.72 ±0.02	3.12 ±0.03	NS	84.77 ±0.04	87.52 ±0.02	2.14
Day 8	4.79 ±0.03	3.07 ±0.05	NS	84.69 ±0.07	87.49 ±0.03	2.14
Day 9	4.71 ±0.04	3.15 ±0.05	NS	84.81 ±0.07	87.54 ±0.03	2.14
Day 10	4.72 ±0.02	2.99 ±0.04	1.67	84.70 ±0.05	87.44 ±0.02	2.16
P > 0.05	NS	NS		NS	NS	

Results are expressed as (Mean ± SEM) of measurements; NS = Not significant at 5% probability level

For daily milk yield, morning mean ranges between 4.71± 0.04 kg and 4.82 ±0.01 kg with day two yielding the most milk volume while day nine recorded the least milk volume with average mean value of 4.76 ±0.01 kg. Meanwhile, the evening milk yield recorded mean value ranging between 2.99 ±0.04 kg to 3.22 ±0.02 kg with day one having the highest yield value and day six having the least respectively. Though there was variation between the morning and the evening milk yield; 4.76 ±0.01 kg and 3.13 ±0.04 kg respectively, the variations were not significantly different at P > 0.05. However, there was a significant different (P < 0.05) between morning and evening quantity of milk produced on day 10 of sample collection. Moisture content showed a variation in the morning and evening milk. For morning milk, it ranged between 84.69 ±0.07 % and 84.90 ±0.07 % with day eight having lowest moisture content and day three having the highest respectively. Average mean was recorded as 84.78 ±0.02 %, constituting 49.21 % of the milk moisture. Whereas the evening variation ranged between 87.44 ±0.02 % and 87.58 ±0.03 % respectively with the highest being day three and the lowest being day ten and average mean value of 87.52 ±0.01 % constituting 50.79 % of the moisture volume. The moisture was generally higher (P < 0.05) in the evening with 87.52 ±0.01 % over the morning with 84.78 ±0.02 %. This result is in

Variations in mineral composition of fresh cow milk

Table 5 Daily variation in sodium, calcium and magnesium contents of fresh cow milk

Sampling Days	Sodium (mg/l)			Calcium (mg/l)			Magnesium (mg/l)		
	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05	Morning	Evening	P < 0.05
Day 1	1943.39 ±1.56	1818.36 ±0.56	14.40	778.92 ±0.20	762.81 ±0.07	5.17	1895.34 ±1.23	1798.92 ±0.42	12.65
Day 2	1946.86 ±1.17	1818.77 ±0.79	14.57	779.36 ±0.15	762.86 ±0.10	5.23	1898.08 ±0.97	1799.23 ±0.59	12.80
Day 3	1946.76 ±5.54	1819.77 ±2.26	14.57	779.34 ±0.70	762.99 ±0.30	5.23	1898.02 ±4.37	1799.99 ±1.70	12.81
Day 4	1950.69 ±2.87	1821.37 ±1.17	14.66	779.84 ±0.36	763.20 ±0.15	5.26	1901.12 ±2.28	1801.19 ±0.88	12.89
Day 5	1951.87 ±3.21	1821.85 ±1.30	14.70	779.98 ±0.40	763.27 ±0.17	5.27	1902.05 ±2.54	1801.55 ±0.98	12.93
Day 6	1953.49 ±3.16	1822.51 ±1.28	14.75	780.19 ±0.40	763.35 ±0.17	5.29	1903.33 ±2.51	1802.05 ±0.97	12.98
Day 7	1954.72 ±2.98	1823.01 ±1.21	14.79	780.34 ±0.37	763.42 ±0.16	5.30	1904.31 ±2.36	1802.42 ±0.91	13.01
Day 8	1952.21 ±5.22	1821.99 ±2.12	14.75	780.03 ±0.66	763.28 ±0.28	5.29	1902.34 ±4.13	1801.66 ±1.60	12.97
Day 9	1953.72 ±5.49	1822.60 ±2.23	14.80	780.21 ±0.69	763.36 ±0.29	5.31	1903.53 ±4.35	1802.12 ±1.68	13.02
Day 10	1961.11 ±3.75	1825.60 ±1.52	15.01	781.14 ±0.47	763.76 ±0.20	5.38	1909.39 ±2.98	1804.38 ±1.15	13.22
P < 0.05	3.23	2.08		1.14	0.76		2.87	1.81	

Results are expressed as (Mean ± SEM) of measurements; NS = Not significant at 5% probability level

consonance with that of Nickerson (2009), whose range is between 85.50 % and 88.77 % respectively.

The daily morning mean value of sodium showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and was observed to range between 1943.39 ± 1.56 mg/l and 1961.11 ± 3.75 mg/l, with highest mean value in day ten and lowest mean value in day one respectively and average mean value of 1951.48 ± 1.57 mg/l. The evening daily mean Na value also showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and ranged between 1818.36 ± 0.56 mg/l and 1825.60 ± 1.52 mg/l, with the highest in day ten and the lowest mean value in day one respectively, and average mean value of 1821.58 ± 0.68 mg/l. However, the morning (51.72 %) mean Na value was higher ($P < 0.05$) than the evening (48.58 %) mean Na value. This showed that the milk samples generally have optimum amount of Na, although the morning mean value was higher while the evening mean value was lower than the range of 1834.87 mg/l to 1951.31 mg/l reported by Damtew and Aregay (2020).

The daily morning mean value of calcium showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and was observed to range between 778.92 ± 0.20 mg/l and 781.14 ± 0.47 mg/l, with highest

mean value in day ten and lowest mean value in day one respectively and average mean value of 779.94 ± 0.20 mg/l. The evening daily mean Ca value also showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and ranged between 762.81 ± 0.07 mg/l and 763.76 ± 0.20 mg/l, with the highest in day ten and the lowest mean value in day one respectively, and average mean value of 763.23 ± 0.09 mg/l. As observed for Na, the mornings (50.54 %) mean Ca value was higher ($P < 0.05$) than the evening (49.46 %) mean value. Both morning and evening Ca mean value were within the range of 758.86 mg/l to 812.75 mg/l reported by Damtew and Aregay (2020). Therefore, the milk sample was also rich in Ca.

The daily morning mean value of magnesium showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and was observed to range between 1895.34 ± 1.23 mg/l to 1909.39 ± 2.98 mg/l, with highest mean value in day ten and lowest mean value in day one respectively and average mean value of 1901.75 ± 1.25 mg/l. The evening daily mean Mg value also showed significant difference at $P < 0.05$, and ranged between 1798.92 ± 0.42 mg/l to 1804.38 ± 1.15 mg/l, with the highest in day ten and the lowest mean value in day one respectively, and average mean value of 1801.35 ± 0.51 mg/l. Similar to Na and Ca, the morning (51.36%)

mean Mg value was higher ($P < 0.05$) than the evening (48.64 %) mean Mg value. Both morning and evening Mg mean value were within the range of 1675.87 mg/l to 2050.65 mg/l reported by Damtew and Aregay (2020), Therefore, the milk sample was also rich in Mg.

Conclusion

The study revealed that cow milk is a complex mixture rich in proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals, with the time of milking playing a crucial role in determining its diurnal composition. The assessment showed that morning milking yielded significantly higher values ($P < 0.05$) for total solids ($11.66 \pm 0.02\%$), solid-not-fat ($7.03 \pm 0.01\%$), fat ($4.63 \pm 0.02\%$), sodium (1951.48 ± 1.57 mg/L), calcium (779.94 ± 0.20 mg/L), and magnesium (1901.75 ± 1.25 mg/L) compared to evening milking. Conversely, evening milking had higher ash content ($0.57 \pm 0.01\%$), protein ($4.49 \pm 0.01\%$), moisture content ($87.52 \pm 0.01\%$), and casein ($3.59 \pm 0.01\%$), although these differences were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The higher nutrient concentration observed in morning milk suggests that it is more suitable for nutrient-rich production, while the increased moisture content in evening milk makes it preferable for

enhancing milk hydration levels. Consequently, time of milking should be prioritized in cow milk production, and further studies are recommended to provide additional insights and reference materials on this subject for future research.

References

- Ahmed, A.A.H., Gald –Sayad, R. and Saynd, M. (2014). Nutritional value and sanitary evaluation of raw camel milk. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 26(4):317 – 326.
- Association of Analytical Chemists (AOAC) (2012). Official methods of analysis. Pp. 1 – 24.
- Damtew, E. T. and Aregay, B. G. (2020). Chemical composition and heavy metals analysis of raw cow's milk. *Journal of Environmental Analytical Toxicology*, 3(2020) 1 – 5.
- Foley, R.C., Bath, D.L., Dickinson, F.N and Tckers, H.A. (2012): Dairy cattle: Principles, Pracices, Problems and profis. Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania pp. 2 – 15.
- Guetouache, M., Guessas, B. and Medjekal, S. (2014). Composition and nutritional value of raw milk. *Biological Sciences*

- and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2(10), 115 – 122.
- Hakoueu, F., Niba, A., Mbiba, F., Adzemye, G., Limnyuy, K. and Isabelle, N. (2021). Lactation length, lactation milk yield and dry off period of exotic and local crossed cows in Cameroon. *Moroccan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2(3), 49 – 55.
- Malacarne, M.P., Franceschi, P., Formaggioni, S., Sandri, P., Mariani and Smmer, A. (2014). Influence of Micellar calcium and phosphorus on rennet coagulation properties of cow's milk. *Journal of Dairy Research*, 81:129 – 136.
- Medhammar, E., Wijesinha-Bettoni, R., Stadlmayr, B., Nilsson, E., Charrondiere, U. R. and Burlingame, B. (2012). Composition of milk from minor dairy animals and buffalo breeds: a biodiversity perspective. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 92(3), 445 – 474.
- Mowang, D. A., Ndome, C. B., Naka, J. B., Ayim, E. M. and Ayame, G. M. (2017). Concentrations of heavy metals in fresh cow milk (Nunu) and Nigerian dwarf goat milk in Calabar, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 4(10): 2394 – 4404.
- Nickerson, S.C. (2009). Milk production: Factors affecting milk composition. In H. F. Aspan, (Ed.), *Milk quality* (pp. 3 – 23). Chapman and Hall, Glasgow, Scotland, UK.
- NIMET (Nigerian Metrological Agency) Nigeria (2017). Climate, weather and water information for sustainable development and safety: Annual Climatic Report.
- Nina, B., Dokic M., Sedak, M. and Solomun, B. (2011). Trace element levels in raw milk from northern and southern regions of Croatia. *Food Chemistry*. 127: 63 – 66.
- Ramesh, C.C. (2016). *Manufacturing Yoghurt and Fermented milk*, 6th edition Blackwell Publishing Ltd Oxford, UK. Pp 7-40.
- Selvaggi, M. (2014). Major Proteins in Doe milk: an update overview on genetic variability. *Molecular Biology Reports*, 41(3), 1035 – 1048.
- Van Hlzen, K.J.E., Sprong, R. C, Van der Meer, R, Van Aredonk, J. A. M. (2019). Genetic and non-genetic variation in concentration of selenium,

calcium, potassium, zinc, magnesium and phosphorous in milk of Dutch Holstein-Friesian cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 92(11), 5752 – 5759.

Walshe, M.J., Grinddle, A, Neji, C. and Benchman M. (2011). Dairy development in Sub-Sahara Africa. *World Bank Technical Paper 135*, African Technical Department series (1 – 20).